

TEACHER'S FACTOR AS A DETERMINANT OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ECONOMICS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OYO STATE, NIGERIA**ADESOPÉ Akinola Olusegun Ph.D**

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Abstracts

The purpose of the study was to assess teacher's factor as a determinant of student's academic achievement in Economics in the public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. The study population consisted of all Economics teachers which is 1,891 in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. 120 teachers were used as sample through multi-stage sampling technique. Descriptive survey design was used. A questionnaire tagged — Teacher's Factor Questionnaire. TFQ ($\alpha = .808$) and an "Economics Achievement Test, EAT ($KR_{21} = .765$) were used to collect the data. Data were analysed using inferential statistics like simple percentage, mean, mean deviation, standard deviation, ANOVA and MANOVA. Results revealed poor level of students' academic achievement in Economics ($\bar{x} = 1.202$, poor level of teacher's factors such as altitude ($\bar{x} = 1.900$), mastery of subject matter ($\bar{x} = 1.953$), experience ($\bar{x} = 2.181$) and educational qualification ($\bar{x} = 2.353$). It was concluded that teacher's factor negatively influenced students' academic achievement in Economics in Public Secondary Schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. It was recommended, among others, that teachers should be trained to improve on their knowledge.

Keywords: Teacher's factors, Students' Academic Achievement, Economics**Introduction**

Academic achievement of secondary school students is very important for the realization of the goals and objectives of education. Given the current state of underdevelopment, unemployment, economic deterioration and consumption based economy of Nigeria today, there is the need for better academic achievement of students, especially in subjects like Economics.

Economics is a social science subject that is studied at the Senior Secondary School (SSS) level. It is concerned with the production, distribution, and consumption of

goods and services. It studies how business, government, and nations like Nigeria make choices about how to locate resources. Aliyu, Dang and Makson (2021) opined that "the guiding principle of Economics subject is the need to equip students with the basic knowledge and skills that will enable them to better appreciate the nature of Economic problems in any society such as Nigeria". An examination of academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Economics therefore becomes imperative.

Understanding of different concepts and skills in economics will lead to good

academic achievement of students in public secondary schools (McCoy, Twyman, Kertterlin-geller & Tindal, 2019). Kenni (2020) perceived it as “how well a public secondary school student is able to assimilate, retain, recall, master, and communicate his or her knowledge of what he or she has learnt in Economics”. In the context of this study, academic achievement of public secondary school students in Economics is viewed as their grades or scores in Economics which determine their academic status and this achievement is as a result of their mental ability, prowess and capacity in the subject in public secondary school setting (Ile & Nwokoye, 2020).

It has however been observed that students' academic achievement in the subject in Oyo State of Nigeria has not been encouraging because the available statistics from West Africa Examinations Council (WAEC) examination results from 2014 to 2021 indicated poor performance of students in Economics in Oyo State. In Economics, 75% of the students scored grades between F9 to D7 within the period under review (WAEC, 2021). The reasons for this poor academic achievement could be due to teacher's factors. The teachers seem not to be qualified or experienced enough to handle the subject. Some of them seem not to have completely mastered the subject and their attitude towards the subject seems to be negative. Therefore, there is the need to examine the extent to which teacher's factors may be influencing students' academic achievement in the subject.

Teacher's factors are those attributes, characteristics and behaviours exhibited by public senior secondary school Economics teachers in the classroom and during teaching and learning process (Bamgbade, Amoo, Oluwadare & Adedokun, 2021). Ile and Nwokoye (2020) said that there are those qualities of a public secondary school Economics teacher that can be measured with tests or derived from their academic or professional records. These teacher's factors could be 'personal' such as age, gender, mental ability, or 'experiential' such as qualification, teaching experience, attitude, subject mastery, teaching styles, questioning behaviour, teaching strategies, just to mention a few (Ile & Nwokoye, 2020). This

paper however focuses on teacher's factors such as teachers' attitude, mastery of subject matter, teaching experience, educational qualification and teaching styles.

Bamgbade, Amoo, Oluwadare and Adedokun (2021) viewed teachers' mastery of subject matter as the ample, up-to-date knowledge of teachers in the subject matter. Commenting on attitude, Safiullah, Muhammad, Hamid and Arshad (2021) in their own assertion said that it is a construct that indicates an Economics teacher like and dislike towards teaching. This may be positive, negative or neutral. Writing on teachers' teaching experience, Bamgbade, Amoo, Oluwadare and Adedokun (2021) opined that “teachers' teaching experience has to do with the increased awareness of diversifying search for new ideas, new commitments and new challenges in Economics Subject”.

Mantero, Casas-Rosal, MazMachado and Rico (2020), in a similar vein, opined that “teachers' educational qualification entails the basic training acquired by an Economics teacher to enable him/her to practice in the teaching profession in public secondary schools”. Teaching styles are methods, procedures and strategies used by an Economics teacher in instruction and interpersonal relations that have developed and matured through years of personal and professional experience. Mantero, Casas-Rosal, MazMachado and Rico (2020) said further that, “it is a combination of manners, tactics and behaviours inherent in the personality of an Economics teacher that immensely influence the teaching-learning process in Public Secondary schools in Oyo State”. Teaching styles could therefore influence students' academic achievement in Economics positively or negatively.

A study of the descriptive-correlation type was carried out by Safiullah, Muhammad, Hamid and Arshad (2021) on the impact of teachers' attitude towards profession on student's academic achievement at secondary school level. The quantitative method was employed while the population consisted of one hundred and forty eight (148) boys' schools, one thousand, six hundred and forty nine (1,649) male teachers and thirty seven thousand, three hundred and twenty four (37,324) boys' students at secondary school at district Peshawar and Charsadda. The cluster

sampling technique was employed to select six hundred (600) male teachers and four hundred (400) boys' students were selected in both districts. Teachers' attitude towards the profession scale was developed to collect data for the study. It consisted of twenty two (22) items and the five-scale Likert rating scale of strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity evidence while Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire which gave a reliability coefficient value of 0.991. However, annual examination of class ten results from the Boards of Intermediate and Secondary Education Peshawar (B1SEP) was used to determine the academic achievement of the students. Specifically, the average score of the student's academic achievement. One thousand (1000) questionnaires were personally distributed to the respondents. Descriptive and Inferential statistical tools such as one sample t-test, Pearson correlation and regression were used for data analysis. These tools were used to test the hypotheses. Results showed that teachers' attitude towards profession positively contributes to students' academic achievement. It was concluded that teachers' attitude towards their profession was significant predictor of students' academic achievement. It was recommended on the basis of the findings that teachers should try as much as possible to develop the right attitude towards teaching for improved academic achievement of the students.

A closely identical study was carried out to investigate the role of teachers' attitude towards their profession on university students' academic performance and classroom environment. Students and teachers at the University of Sargodha made up the population of the study. These participants were selected from the Department of Psychology from Faculty of Social Sciences, Department of Statistics from Faculty of Sciences and Department of Communication and Media Studies from Faculty of Arts and Humanities at the University. Data were collected online. Attitude scale towards teaching profession and classroom environment scale were used to gather data for the research. Perceptions of teachers were recorded using classroom

environment scale and Teachers' attitude scale, while student's academic performance was measured through self-reported CGPA. Data were analyzed using mediation analysis via Statistical Package for Social Science Software version 22. It was concluded, based on the results of the study, that the mediating role of teachers' attitude towards their profession on University Students' academic performance and classroom environment was statistically significant. It was therefore recommended that students' academic achievement may be made better by focusing on creating classroom environment that is more structured and well designed; secondly, all hands must be on deck in ensuring that teachers have the right attitude towards their profession for improved academic performance of the students at the various departments in the university.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that students' academic achievement in Economics subject has not been encouraging because the available statistics from West Africa Examinations Council (WAEC) examination results from 2014 to 2021 shows poor performance of students in economics in Oyo state, Nigeria. The reasons for this poor academic achievement of students in Economics could be due to class size, teacher factors, learning environment, learners' attitude and so on. There is therefore the need to examine the extent to which these teacher's factors may be influencing students' academic achievement in the subject.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate teacher's factors as determinants of academic achievement of students in Economics in public secondary schools in Oyo State.

Research Question

What factors influence teaching of Economics in public secondary schools in Oyo State?

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between teacher's factors (attitude, mastery of subject matter, teaching experience, educational qualification, and teaching styles) and students' academic achievement in

Economics in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was used to carry out this study and it focuses on teacher’s factors such as teachers’ attitudes, mastery of subject-matter, teaching experience, teaching styles and educational

qualifications. Also, a self-constructed questionnaire titled "Teacher’s Factors Questionnaire (TFQ)" was used to collect data for the study. Data were analysed using inferential statistics like simple percentage, mean, mean deviation, standard deviation, ANOVA and MANOVA.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of all the public senior secondary school Economics teachers in Oyo State. Nigeria.

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/N	Senatorial District	No. of Public Sec. Schools	No of Public Sec. School Economics teachers
3.	Oyo Central	244	737
	Oyo North	171	519
	Oyo South	210	635
	Sub-Total	625	1,891

Source: Teaching Service Commission (TESCOM), 2022

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select Sixty (60) secondary schools from the three (3) senatorial districts in the state.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Demographic Data Analysis

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Economics Teachers' Demographic Variables

Demographic Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Gender	Male	50	41.67
	Female	70	58.33
	Total	120	100
Age	20-30 years	30	25.00
	31-40	39	32.50
	41-50'	50	41.67
	51-60	01	1.62
	Total	120	100
Highest educational qualifications	NCE	30	25.00
	Bachelor's degree	70	58.33
	PGDE	05	4.17
	Master's degree	15	3.47
	MPhil/Doctorate degree	0	0.00
Total	120	100	
Years of teaching experience	5-10 years	5	4.17
	11-15 years	5	4.17
	16-20 years	30	25.00
	Above 20 years	85	70.83
	Total	120	100

Source: Fieldwork. 2022

Table 2 shows the frequency distribution of Economics teachers' demographic variables in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria (Oyo Central, Oyo North and Oyo South). Analysis of Economics teachers' gender reveals more female to male Economics teachers as the table shows that 41.67% are males and 58.33% are females. The age of the Economics teachers reveals that 25% are within 20-30 years of age, 32.5% are within 31-40 years of age, 41.67% are within 41-50 years of age and the remaining 1.67% are between 51-60 years of age. The educational qualification of Economics teachers shows that 25% of them have NCE as their highest educational qualification,

58.33% have Bachelor's degree, 4.17% have PGDE, 3.47% have Master's as their highest educational qualification. This result implies that the majority of the teachers are university graduates. In terms of the teachers' years of teaching experience, 4.17% of them have within 5-10 years of teaching experience. 4.17% of them have within 11-15 years of teaching experience. 25.00% of them have within 16-20 years of teaching experience while 70.83% of them have above 20 years of teaching experience. This result implies that most of the Economics teachers are vastly experienced.

Research Question: What factors influence teaching of Economics in public secondary schools in Oyo State?

Table 3: Teachers' Attitude towards the Teaching of Economics (n = 840)

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean (x)	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Teachers' Attitude	05	10	10	105	2.298	864	Disagree (low)
2.	Teachers' Mastery of Subject Matter	04	09	11	36	1.824	1.120	Disagree (low)
3.	Teachers' Experience	09	11	10	30	2.073	1.223	Disagree (low)
4.	Teachers' Qualifications	05	10	05	40	1.820	1.119	Disagree
5.	Teachers' Teaching Styles	25	15	05	15	1.948	1.271	Agree (High)

Criterion Mean = 2.500; Weighted Mean = 1.926; SD = 1.019; Overall Decision = Disagree (Low) Source: Fieldwork. 2022

Key: SA = Strongly Agree (4), A = Agree (3), D = Disagree (2), SD = Strongly Disagree (1), Std. Dev = Standard Deviation

Mean **Threshold:** If the mean is 0.000-1.499 = Strongly Disagree (Very Bad); 1.500-2.499 = Disagree (Bad); 2.500-3.499 = Agree (Good) and 3.500 to 4.000 = Strongly Agree (Very Good)

Table 3 presents the teacher's factors towards the teaching of Economics in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The

rating scale of strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (4) was used. The criterion mean was set at 2.500 which implies that any

mean below 2.500 falls within the section of "disagree" while any mean at 2.500 and above falls within the section of "agree". Eight (8) items were used to determine the teachers' - attitude, towards the teaching of Economics in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. All items were positive. All of the items were remarked "disagree", since their means fall within 1.500-2.499. The teachers disagreed that they have vast knowledge of teaching methods, value their teaching profession, display positive emotions during teaching, have good feeling about their teaching job. allow classroom interactions with the students, get energized and happy during the teaching of economics and that teaching economics subject is useful to them. This result implies that the attitude of Economics teachers is poor or negative which

is bad. The weighted mean (SD) of 1.900 (1.123) confirms that the attitude of Economics teachers towards the teaching of Economics in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria is generally bad or negative. This result suggests that the teachers have unfavourable attitude towards the teaching of Economics subject in the study area.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between teacher’s factors (attitude, mastery of subject matter, teaching experience, educational qualification, and teaching styles) and students' academic achievement in Economics in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State.

Multiple Regression Analysis and Model Summary (MANOVA)

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Regression	1559.322	6	259.887	9.961	.000	High Significance
Residual	21732.373	833	26.089			
Total	23291.695	839				

Model Summary: R = .259, R Square = .067, Adjusted R Square = .060, Standard Error of the Estimate = 5.10777

Source: Field Work, 2022

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of the study was to assess teacher’s factors as determinants of student’s academic achievement in the public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. Hypothesis shows that teacher’s factors (attitude, mastery of subject matter, experience, qualifications and teaching styles) has influence on students’ academic achievements in Economics. The finding is supported by a work on "The Effect of Teaching Method of Economics on Students Performance: A Case Study of Selected Secondary Schools in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria" which revealed that teaching methods or styles of teachers significantly determine students' academic performance in Economics in Lagos State.

South-west, Nigeria (Safiullah, Muhammad, Hamid & Arshad, 2021).

A study on Teachers’ Qualifications, Class Size and Teaching Experience as Predictors of Achievement in Senior Secondary School Physics in Oyo State, Nigeria showed a relative significant influence of class size on students' academic achievement in Physics in Oyo State, Southwestern Nigeria. The finding is also in line with the work on "Teachers' Qualification, Attitude and Mastery of Content as Correlates of Students' Academic Achievement in Economics in Lagos State, Nigeria" which revealed that teachers' attitude and mastery of content significantly correlate with students' academic achievement in Economics while teachers' qualification had no significant correlation with students' academic achievement in Economics in Lagos State, Southwest, Nigeria. Similarities observed in both studies could be because both were carried out in the Southwest region of Nigeria (Lagos and Oyo States) (Zunaira, Ashfaque & Naila, 2022).

Conclusion

This research examined teacher' factors as determinants of academic achievement of students in economics in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings revealed poor level of academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in Economics; it revealed poor level of teacher factors such as teachers' attitude, teachers' mastery of subject matter, teachers' experience and teachers' educational qualification but good level of teachers' teaching styles. On the basis of the results, it can be concluded that poor performance of teachers in terms of attitude, teachers' mastery of subject matter and teachers' teaching styles are the cause of poor level of academic achievement of the students in Economics in public senior secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. It can also be concluded that although Economics teachers' experience and educational qualifications were poor, they are not responsible for the poor level of academic achievement of the students in Economics.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are therefore given on the basis of the findings of the study:

1. Economics as a subject play a vital role in helping students to understand and tackle the economic challenges facing the nation. As such, there is need for more attention to be given to the academic achievement of students in the subject;
2. Economics teachers' factors such as attitude, mastery of subject matter, teaching experience, educational qualification were all found to be poor as shown in this study. Educational stakeholders and school heads should try as much as possible to organize seminars, conferences and symposiums for teachers to improve themselves especially their attitude and mastery of subject matter;
3. Economics teachers who are well experienced and qualified should be recruited to teach at the public secondary school level; and,
4. Government and educational stakeholders should try as much as possible to ensure that all the needed

material resources such as library resource, ICT, instructional materials like visual, audio and audio-visual aids are provided and adequate. These material resources can help the teachers to better impact the students with what they have learnt and trained to do.

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